

A novel method to conduct sensor calibration with virtually simulated images

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Abstract

Autonomous vehicles have created a shift in manufacturing processes in production plants. Nowadays, starting from the factory planning, line setup and testing of the vehicle are first carried out via simulation and are analysed. In order for autonomous systems to drive safely, they are equipped with a huge number of sensors; one among them are Multi Camera Systems (MCS). With the process knowledge of the Camera Calibration in the Production plants, the same process concept is built in Carla-Unreal Engine Software. The results of the calibration in different environmental conditions with the virtual world images are compared with the results of the real-world calibration. **Keywords:** Virtual Simulation, sensor calibration, autonomous vehicle.

Introduction

Digital manufacturing implementation is easier with set of methods and technological tools via simulation software's. Simulation helps in validation of the experiment, process, and product design. The system design and configuration are validated with simulation. Simulation is gaining much importance due to the shift in the manufacturing environment due to Industrialisation. Due to the fast-changing markets, the companies need to quickly customise and personalise according to the conditions, where simulation is necessary¹. The research activities in the area of simulation are increasing every year, which can be observed in the Figure 1.1 below.

Figure 1.1: Publication in Simulation Domain¹

Simulation helps in understanding the complex systems in a better way due to the scope of visualisation with the animations and graphics. Information's in huge amount can be processed quickly without any difficulty in simulation with help of animations and graphics. Simulations are used to process in many areas such as verification and validation, analysis of the result, communication of results, Getting buy-in from nonbelievers and Achieving credibility for the simulation².

The manufacturing technology has been improved with the advent of virtual simulation and virtual reality. The modelling of the production line with the help of simulation technology has revolutionised the production organisation, with the advent of 3C, which are Communication, Computer and Control. This has led to a change from the traditional manufacturing practices³. Due to the competitive manufacturing market, adapt-ability to the change and quick response to the market condition is very vital. Due to which, the resources and assembly lines are configured rapidly⁴. The overall equipment utilization could be improved by changing the process sequence or developing a new assembly⁵, which can be visualised with virtual simulation. With the VR technology, one can render the three-dimensional Virtual environment on the computer with graphics and animations⁶. The assembly line planning is a process, based on the type of the product and capacity requirement; the equipment's are selected and arranged in manufacturing sequence such that the equipment is utilised with maximum effectiveness and the assembly line functions smoothly⁷. The assembly line can be simulated in the virtual environment with the product capacity data in the early stages of the project, which helps in making the decision. Hence, we can shorten the time for the planning the layout and calculating the risk factors theoretically.

Camera calibration in Real World

The assembly process of a modern vehicle in the factory line is presented in Figure 1.2. Before the vehicle moves to the final stage for checking, the vehicle is integrated with the electrical parts in the Trim line. In the chassis assembly station, the and drive train and the engine are integrated. At the Final stage, which is the end of line check for the alignment of the wheel, adjustment of the headlamp, brake/ABS test in carried on the test bench. In this stage, also

the ADAS functionality needs to be calibrated and also validated before it moves out of the production plants. With the advent of technologies, new methods need to be explored to calibrate, check the functionality of the sensor and to validate its property in the production line. The end of line is very critical, as it needs to make sure that all the systems which are integrated in the vehicle function as expected. Usually, at the end of line assembly step takes around 1.5 to 5 minutes⁸. When a problem is detected at the end of line, the vehicle moves back to the area where it needs to be reworked and checked. The requirements for good camera calibration are good light conditions, vehicle standing on level floor, tyre pressure correctly, Trunk empty, fuel tank 90% filled, steering straight ahead, Wheels & Suspension aligned (thrust line), Steering angle sensors adjusted, Vehicles with air-suspension in service mode, Windshield and camera eye clean, all doors closed, Targets aligned according to OEM specification and Battery support unit / charger connected.

Figure 1.2: End of Line Testing⁸

Calibration Process in Off-Highway Vehicle Sector

The common technique used for Calibration in off highway vehicles is the static calibration. The objective of static calibration is to determine position and orientation of the camera within the vehicle. This allows to compensate the mechanical tolerances in the installation of the camera via software. It serves as a quality gate both at customer end of line for the basic functionality & proper installation of the camera and at repair workshops. It enables functional performance.

The calibration at the end of the line in the factory is performed by placing the calibration markers on the ground and the position of these markers are fixed and predetermined. After the calibration process, the validations are performed to validate the camera calibrated properties.

Figure 1.3: Calibration Tool for Cameras and Radar Sensor⁹

Development of the Virtual environment in Unreal Engine The first step before building virtual environment is to validate the mounting height and angle of the camera sensor. Hence, these results are validated in the real-world experiments at varying mounting angle and mounting height. These mounting dimensions of the camera is implemented in the virtual environment software.

After performing the experiments in the real world under different case scenarios such as in Bright light condition (1000 lx) and dull light condition (200 lx), we validate the results of the real-world test with the virtual environment.

Requirements for Virtual Environment

For performing Vehicle in loop testing, initially we need a software to create the virtual environment. The images captured in the virtual environment is fed to the calibration tool for calibration. The steps needed to perform calibration with the simulation environment images:

- Creation of simulation environment with Unreal Engine 4
- Mounting of the camera sensor and image capturing in Unreal Engine 4
- Simulated images feeding to the calibration tool
- Analysis of the extrinsic parameters result and validation of the simulated results in ADTF software
- Performing similar test for different environmental conditions and comparing the results
- Finally compare the results of simulation environment with the experiments per-formed in the real world with vehicle

Figure 1.4: Images from the Unreal Engine

Results

The correlation between the real and virtual world calibration can be discussed by comparing the slope of the equation of the line for the calibration output for bright and night lighting conditions. Here in the graph, the bright light condition is assumed 1 and night light condition is assumed 0.

C2W Correlation

The C2W correlation for the bright and night light condition is illustrated below in Figure 1.5. By comparing the slopes of the virtual and real-world calibration, the slope deviation between them is 0.01.

Figure 1.5: C2W correlation between real and virtual environment

Marker Detection Correlation

The Marker Detection correlation for the bright and night light condition is illustrated below in Figure 1.6. By comparing the slopes of the virtual and real-world calibration, the slope deviation between them is 0.25.

Figure 1.6: Marker Detection correlation between real and virtual environment

These correlations prove that, the virtual simulation calibration approach is in line with the real-world calibration procedure.

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